

Questionnaire - Section I (Criminal Law - general part)

Traditional Criminal Law Categories and AI: Crisis or Palingenesis?

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Authors:

István AMBRUS
Krisztina KARSAI
Norbert KIS
Barna MISKOLCZI
Erzsébet MOLNÁR
Mónika NOGEL

Introduction

In Hungary, there is no robot law yet. However, a government-backed AI Strategy (Strategy) was created in 2020. The Strategy draws up a detailed and ambitious Action Plan, three subparagraphs of which set up deadlines (2021) for elaborating the general and sectoral framework of the regulation (30/06/2021) and a code of ethics (30/04/2021) as well. The framework, however, is still under preparation. Criminal law was not on the Agenda of the Action Plan, not even in the sectoral framework. Research on the possible hazards of the digital age in the criminal law field had been started by experts and practitioners way before the Strategy.

Consequently, a map of challenges has been drawn up in 11 categories, one of them dealing with harms possibly caused by a future AI. This work is run by a government agency (Digital Welfare Program Ltd.). The goal is to give tools and hints to the ministry responsible for codification of the Criminal Code and the Criminal Procedure Code, to help identify the most obvious (and, in the case of AI, not so obvious) hazards of digitalisation, and to help to prepare amendments to those Codes in case of necessity. However, no modifications have been made with the help of this work so far.

No case law has developed concerning the traditional categories of criminal law's General Part, but there has been a lively debate on the topic of AI in academic circles and tabloids too. This debate is more about AI ethics than AI criminal law in connection with the components of the offence (actus reus, mens rea, culpability) on the one hand and with the aims of punishments on the other hand.

Furthermore, the academic debate is currently carried out on the possible application of algorithmic decision-making solutions within the justice ecosystem.

The academic debate comes in conferences, books, and articles and by launching research projects and establishing research labs and institutions dedicated for this thematical areas.¹ For instance, the AI conference organised by the University of Public Service (2020) discussed private law, administrative law and – at some point –

¹ Digicrimjus 2020-1-HU01-KA203-078670, New challenges for teaching, researching and practicing criminal law in the digital age. www.digicrimjus.com (University of Szeged in consortium with University of Konstanz and University of Istanbul); Information Society Resesarch Centre (University of Public Servisce); Artificial Intelligence Research Laboratory (Hungarian Academy of Science)

criminal law aspects of AI. One of the consequences of the conference was that there were many valuable thoughts, but there was no common background; there was no common philosophical platform based on which a regulation could be built. The books published on AI's criminal law aspects are still scarce and concentrate mainly on the applicability of AI in criminal justice or the problematics of liability. In the case of the latter topic, the authors tend to exclude the criminal liability of the „strong” AI from the subjects of exploration, many of the researchers being sceptic about the possibility of such AI, thinking of the technological singularity as „science fiction”.² Other researchers admit the possibility of “strong” AI, and the necessity of dealing with it.

Questions (When answering the questions, you may tick more than one box)

A) Definition and legal qualification of Artificial Intelligence system (AI system)

1) Is there a legal definition of an AI system in your domestic law?

No, there is no such definition in Hungarian domestic law.

If not, could you please indicate whether:

- (1) there is a definition in the case-law
- (2) it is possible to infer this definition from other legal sources
- (3) your national lawmaker plans a legal reform to define this concept. If so, please provide a short description
- (4) there is a definition elaborated by the scholars (e.g. in the field of criminal law, civil law, administrative law, labour law)

There are some definitions in the literature: one group uses the concepts of “autonomy” and “human-like behaviour”, others identify it with “machine learning”. The legal literature uses technical engineering literature and general concepts as a starting point. Most scholars consider algorithmic decision-making and machine learning central to the concept.

2) Is there a different legal definition of *Machine Learning* in your domestic law?

- a) If so, could you please:
 - (1) quote it (in English and your language)
 - (2) clarify the areas of law (e.g. criminal law, civil law, administrative law, labour law, etc.) it refers to
 - (3) indicate whether it includes the concept of AI

There is no definition of ML in Hungarian domestic law.

b) If not, could you please indicate whether:

² Books in Hungarian: Bernát TÖRÖK – Zsolt ZÓDI (ed.): Regulation challenges of Artificial Intelligence. University of Public Service, Ludovika Publishing Office, Budapest, 2021; Krisztián FEHÉR – Attila KÖKÉNYESI-BARTOS – Barnabás BÁRTFAI: AI as Pandora's Digital Boks. BBS-Info Ltd. Budapest, 2020; Barna MISKOLCZI – Zoltán SZATHMÁRY: Criminal Law Challenges in the Age of Informations – Big Data, Profiling and AI. HVG ORAC, Budapest, 2018. Articles in English: István AMBRUS: Rethinking the essential elements of substantive criminal law in the light of Artificial Intelligence, REVIEW OF CENTRAL AND EAST EUROPEAN LAW , 22 p. (2022); Krisztina KARSAI: Algorithmic Decisions within the Criminal Justice Ecosystem and their Problem Matrix. INTERNATIONAL REVIEW OF PENAL LAW / REVUE INTERNATIONALE DE DROIT PENAL 92 : 1 pp. 13-30. , 18 p. (2021)

- (1) there is a definition in the case-law
- (2) it is possible to infer this definition from other legal sources or soft law

3) Does your domestic law confer legal personhood or legal capacity to the AI systems?

Hungarian domestic law does not confer legal personhood or legal capacity to the AI systems.

- a) If not, could you please indicate:
 - (1) whether the lawmaker in your country has planned/plans legal reforms to confer legal personhood upon AI systems
 - (2) whether scholars suggested conferring legal personhood or legal capacity upon AI systems

There is a broad consensus in the current literature that risks arising from AI and ethical concerns and goals should be handled without giving legal personhood to AI systems.

4) In regulating AI applications, which is the preferred approach? Is it general, applicable to all kinds of AI applications, or sectoral (e.g. applicable only to specific sectors, such as drones, facial recognition, autonomous driving, etc.)?

There are no specific regulations in the Hungarian legal order.

5) In which areas are automatised and autonomous decision-making processes by AI systems forbidden? If available, please refer to new proposals.

There is no such ban. The only applicable rule is in Info tv. (Act CXII of 2011 on Informational Self-Determination and Freedom of Information ("Privacy Act"), which re-iterates GDPR's authority³ on automated decision making. According to this "Section 6

A decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces adverse effects concerning the person or the legitimate interests of the data subject, or produces legal results significantly affecting him shall only be made if an explicit authorisation is provided in an Act or a binding legal act of the European Union and provided that.

- a) it does not violate the requirement of equal treatment,
- b) the controller or the processor acting on behalf of, or instructed by, the controller
- ba) informs the data subject, upon his request, of the method and the criteria applied during the decision-making mechanism, bb) reviews upon the data subject's request, the result of the decision by using human intervention, and
- c) unless otherwise provided by an Act or a binding legal act of the European Union, no sensitive data are used in the decision making."

The LED Directive⁴ was also incorporated into the domestic legal order by the above-

³ European Union's framework for data protection: REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

⁴ Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA

mentioned Info tv., with content entirely in line with the Directive. However, it provided a transitional period to ensure technical compliance with automated data processing—this exemption from strict recording obligations until 31 December 2022 in case of extreme difficulty or cost.

B) Existing criminal offences and criminalisation

1) Have traditional offences and cybercrimes already been applied to an illegal act committed by, through or against an AI system?

Not yet.

a) If so, could you please specify what offences have been applied, providing case law references and a brief description of them?

b) If not, could you please:

(1) indicate whether there are legal reforms or law proposals at issue

In Hungary, there is no AI law yet. However, a government-backed AI Strategy (Strategy) was created in 2020. The framework is still under preparation.

(2) indicate whether, according to the legal literature, there are offences already applicable to illegal acts involving AI systems (if so, please specify)

In Hungarian criminal law, the most frequent criminal offence in connection with AI may be the *violation of information systems or related data breach* (section 423 of the Criminal Code), which may be regarded as the prototype of delicts related to the computer, according to former terminology, and recently against information systems. This could, for example, be a DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attack controlled by AI. However, it is also characteristic that this act is only a predicate offence for a further crime committed by data manipulation or other infringement after logging into the information system. A violation of information systems takes place for illicit gain and in a form causing damage; essentially, *information system fraud* may be established (section 375 of the Criminal Code), which overshadows the offence mentioned formerly (statutory unit). Although, other criminal crimes committed through information systems, such as “simple” *fraud* (section 373 of the Criminal Code) or *extortion* (section 367 of the Criminal Code), may be established in concurrence with the violation of information systems or related data breach. Similarly, an “easy” criminal situation may be created by AI, for example, to commit *misuse of personal data* (section 219 of the Criminal Code), *abuse of classified data* or *violation of trade secrets* (section 418 of the Criminal Code).

Harassment (section 222 of the Criminal Code), albeit frequently occurring in classic “offline” form and increasing in cyberspace, may be committed by the use of AI as well. Notably, the variant committed by disturbance under section 222(1) of the Criminal Code may be envisaged through hundreds or thousands of emails, system notices, etc., generated automatically by AI. Unfortunately, the type of harassment committed by threat under section 222(2)(a) may be established in the same way, although the content of the message sent by AI is also relevant here.

In the context of sexual crimes, *child pornography* (section 204 of the Criminal Code)

may come into question, which can be widely distributed on the internet. It can be highlighted that recent Anglo-Saxon literature also focuses on new types of sexual offences developed under the influence of AI. The so-called *sex boots*, now often with a humanoid appearance, may serve to satisfy acceptable sexual needs and simulate *sexual violence* (section 197 of the Criminal Code). Even if we disregard the issue of whether AI may be a legally recognised entity in the future against which such an offence may be committed – it may have a criminogenic effect on future sexual delicts committed against a human, according to the related research.⁵

2) Has your domestic law introduced new offences related to designing, programming, developing, producing, functioning or using AI systems?

Not yet.

3) Has your domestic law introduced new criminal offences concerning acts committed through or against an AI system?

Not yet.

a) If not, could you please indicate:

- (1) whether the lawmaker in your country has planned/plans legal reforms to introduce new criminal offences related to AI systems (please quote them in English and in your language)
- (2) whether reports or legal literature suggest the introduction of new criminal offences linked to AI systems (please also provide bibliographic references)

In Hungary, there is no AI law yet. However, a government-backed AI Strategy (Strategy) was created in 2020. The framework is still under preparation.

4) Does your domestic law provide for positive obligations for persons and legal person designing, developing, producing, testing, selling or distributing AI systems

Not yet.

5) Does your domestic law provide specific legal obligations for users of AI systems?

Not yet.

C) Applicability of Traditional Criminal Law Categories

1) According to your domestic law and jurisprudence, is the AI system considered a “computer system” as defined by Article 1, lett. a) of Cybercrime Convention and Article 2, lett. a) of Directive EU/2013/40?

Act C of 2012 on the Criminal Code (Hungarian Criminal Code - HCC) defines an information system as follows (Point 15 Art. 1 § 459): the equipment providing for the automatic processing, management, storage, transmission of data, or the totality of

⁵ István AMBRUS: AI and criminal law [in Hungarian]. *Állam- és Jogtudomány* 2020/4., 4-23. p.

such equipment in connection with each other. Information systems, including computer processing memory units, differ from the 'traditional' computers (e.g. public pay telephony, information systems communications systems, telecommunications systems, etc.).⁶

This term fully corresponds to the term used in the Convention and the Directive.

2) In your national system, are there other definitions applicable to AI systems despite not expressly referring to them?

No.

3) Have the existing offences (see B 1. a) already been applied to illegal acts related to or connected to AI systems (e.g. designing, programming, developing, producing, making use of an AI system)? Which traditional criminal law categories (e.g. action, omission, causation requirement, the mental element, direct liability, etc.) have been applied or extended to these cases?

Not yet.

On a theoretical level, professional risks can be highlighted in terms of the liability of the AI producer and programmer. According to Paragraph 165 (1) of the HCC, "Any person who, by violating a professional rule, puts the life, limb or health of another or others in imminent danger or causes bodily harm negligently shall be punishable for a misdemeanour by imprisonment for a term of one to five years."

It is doubtful whether the producer or programmer of the AI can be held liable for this crime. The result of the offence is imminent danger, which is a concrete threat to a specific person and situation. However, this criterion is certainly not present at the moment of production.

The literature is mainly concerned with the applicability of traffic offences to the punishable offences committed by AI.⁷ However, there have been no prosecutions for offences where human influence has not been required. A person commits the offence of causing a road traffic accident (HCC § 235), "Who, by violating the road rules, causes serious bodily injury to another person or others through negligence." The driver's liability can be established if the vehicle is not entirely self-driving, and the driver has to keep or monitor the driving under human control. Failure to do so will constitute an offence. If the vehicle is fully self-driving and the driver cannot intervene, no liability can be established in the absence of misconduct.

4) Are there specific problems concerning the principle of legality?

No.

5) Is analogy admissible? Has it been used to criminalise illegal acts related to AI systems?

⁶ Kitti MEZEI: Actual Questions of Cyber Crimes [in Hungarian]. In: Magyar Jogászegyleti Értekezések. Magyar Közlöny Lap- és Könyvkiadó. Budapest, 157-173. 159. p.

⁷ István AMBRUS: Traffic Criminal Law in the XXIst Century and Self-Driving Cars [in Hungarian] Társadalomtudományi Kutatóközpont Jogtudományi Intézet, Budapest, 2020. 121-132. p.

- a) If so, please provide, if available, examples describing paradigmatic cases and give a brief description of the criminal conduct (*actus reus*) and other elements of the crime

No, applying an analogy that establishes or extends the perpetrator's criminal liability is prohibited by the principle of *nullum crimen sine lege, nulla poena sine lege* (Art. XXVIII 3 of Hungarian Fundamental Law of 2011). There have been no cases in Hungary where criminal liability has been established by analogy.

- 6) Are the provisions concerning attempted crime applicable to AI-related crimes? Are there already cases of AI-related crimes qualified as attempted crimes?

No.

- 7) Is it possible to apply existent rulings of joint-perpetration and participation in the commission of the crime to AI-related crimes? Who can be considered a joint perpetrator or participant in the commission of the crime (please refer to both human and artificial agents)? Is the "perpetration-by-another" liability model applicable?

The programmer of the AI might be liable as an accessory by omission to an offence committed by the user of the AI if he knew that the offence had been committed. The "committed by others" model of liability is currently not applicable in the Hungarian criminal law system for punishable acts committed by AI because it has no normative basis. The HCC recognises this form of liability, but it is very narrowly regulated, currently only in military criminal law and about active official corruption and budget fraud. However, it should be noted that these forms of liability are not applied in case law.⁸

- 8) Could legal persons be held criminally liable for AI-related crimes committed for their benefit in your domestic law? If so, please give some examples

The Hungarian legal system has acknowledged the criminal sanctionability of legal persons since 2001 (in force since 2004).

Paragraph 2(1) of Act CIV of 2001 on Criminal Measures against Legal Persons states that criminal measures may be applied against a legal person for the intentional commission of an offence as defined by the Hungarian Criminal Code if the offence was committed with the purpose or effect of obtaining an advantage for the benefit of the legal person, or if the offence was executed using the legal person and the offence was committed by the legal person.

(a) by its manager or a member authorised to represent it, its employee or officer, its managing director or a member of its supervisory board, or by their delegates, in the course of the legal person's business,

(b) the member or employee committed the offence within the scope of the legal person's activities, and the fulfilment of the duty of management or control by the manager, the company secretary or the supervisory board could have prevented the commission of the offence.

According to paragraph 2, criminal measures may also be applied against a legal person if the offence was committed for the benefit of the legal person or was committed using the legal person and the manager or member of the legal person's management or staff authorised to represent the legal person, or the manager or member of the supervisory board knew that the

⁸ Erzsébet MOLNÁR: Special Criminal Responsibility of Leaders of Companies [in Hungarian]. Iurisperitus Kiadó, Szeged, 2020.

offence had been committed.

9) Are forms of secondary liability applicable to AI-related crimes?

No. There are no underlying forms of liability in the current HCC that can be used to establish the liability of AI. Also, the criminal law only allows for the liability of a natural person (except the sanctioning for a legal person) in terms of underlying forms of liability.

10) Is the wording of existing offences (particularly computer crimes and cybercrimes) capable of including illegal acts committed through or against an AI system?

a) If so, briefly explain the technical-legal wording of the applicable offence(s) and refer, if available, to some concrete cases

b) If not, briefly explain why the existing offences cannot be applied

The Hungarian Criminal Code has a separate chapter on offences specifically against information systems (Chapter XLIII).

Violation of information systems or related data breach

423 (1) A person who logs into an information system without authorisation by violating or circumventing a technical measure safeguarding that information system or stays logged in exceeding or violating the limits of his authorisation to log in is guilty of a misdemeanour and shall be punished by imprisonment for up to two years.

(2) A person who

a) hinders the functioning of an information system without authorisation or violating the limits of his authorisation, or

b) modifies, deletes or renders inaccessible any data stored in an information system without authorisation or violating the limits of his authorisation is guilty of a felony and shall be punished by imprisonment for up to three years.

(3) The punishment shall be imprisonment for one to five years for committing a felony if the criminal offence specified in paragraph (2) affects a significant number of information systems.

(4) The punishment shall be imprisonment for two to eight years if the criminal offence is committed against a public interest enterprise.

(5) For this section, data means the representation of facts, information, and terms stored, processed, technically processed or transferred in the information system in a manner that is suitable for being processed by the information system, including any program that implements a function of the information system.

To establish the offence, the information system must be protected by technical measures, and this protection must be active, i.e. have a user ID and password, firewall or other security. It is also essential that the offence is accessed by breaching or circumventing the protection measure, but it is irrelevant how this may be done.⁹ It can also happen through AI-assisted phishing.

The existing rules on fraud committed using an information system are objectively capable of penalising unlawful acts committed against AI. The provision reads as follows:

Article 375 (1) Any person who, for unlawful gain, enters data into an information system, alters, deletes or renders inaccessible the data processed therein, or interferes with the operation of the information system by performing any other function, and thereby causes damage, shall be punished by a criminal offence punishable by imprisonment for up to three years. The offence is qualified according to the degree of damage caused. By the

⁹ See MEZEI *ibid.*

international definition of information system, the offence also includes an extension to offences committed using cash substitutes: (5) Any person who causes damage by using a counterfeit, falsified or unauthorised electronic means of payment or by accepting payment by such means shall also be punished.

11) Please clarify whether, for criminal liability, the state of mind (e.g. *dolus*) on the part of the human agent who designed (programmed or developed or produced or circulated or marketed or used) the AI system shall include the exact and concrete modus operandi of the AI system in committing the offence.

There is no established domestic literature or practice on this issue. The consciousness of the AI producer, designer and programmer must embrace the modus operandi of AI. Only in this case can they be charged with intentional criminality. For example, if the AI is knowingly (intentionally or with conscious negligence) programmed so that it (also) realises criminal offences, the AI producer or programmer can be held liable given the result. However, the user's knowledge need not encompass the AI's operating and learning mechanisms. A user is responsible for the commission of a criminal offence only if his or her knowledge encompasses the objective elements of the offence, including the fact that he or she is using AI to engage in the conduct constituting the offence. If his or her knowledge does not grasp this fact because he or she is unaware of the AI's operating mechanism, he or she cannot be held liable for intentional criminal wrongdoing. However, the perpetrator may be responsible for reckless negligence if he could reasonably have been expected to know the modus operandi.

12) Assuming that the crime is caused by the autonomous "conduct" of the AI system, could the person who designed/programmed/developed/produced/sold/used the AI system be held criminally liable if he knew about its autonomous learning and decision-making capacity?

a) If so, could you please indicate the subjective prerequisite for criminality (specific intent, general intent, direct intent, *dolus eventualis*, negligence, etc.). Could you provide some examples?

This is not possible under the current criminal law system, which is still based on the principle of guilt and requires a causal link between the act and the result.

At most, negligence can be a form of guilt that can be suitable for this since we do not require knowledge or foresight, and the basis for the establishment of liability is the failure to exercise due care. § 8 of the Hungarian Criminal Code: " A criminal offence is committed by negligence by the person who foresees the possible consequences of his/her conduct but carelessly trusts in their non-occurrence; as well as by the person who does not foresee the possibility of the consequences because he fails to pay the attention or prudence that may be expected of him/her."

Suppose the perpetrator could have been expected, based on the professional rules applicable to him, to have prepared the AI with such care, taking into account its learning capacity, that the commission of a punishable offence was excluded. In that case, the possibility of liability is not banned in principle. However, this would be an excessive extension of criminal liability from both an objective and a subjective point of view.

13) Are there in your domestic legal system cases of criminal liability for negligent or reckless conduct which can be applied when a crime or an illegal result is caused by conduct consisting of programming, producing or making use of an AI system?

a) If so, please point out the differences between negligent/reckless conducts carried out by designers/programmers/producers/sellers and by users or persons with a specific duty of care

Please provide examples describing paradigmatic cases, giving a brief

description of criminal conduct (actus reus) of offences deemed to be applicable, and please specify if there are cases of corporate criminal liability.

Homicide (HCC § 160) and bodily injury (HCC § 164) are also punishable in the case of the negligent commission. This means that if a designer, producer or programmer, in the course of creating an AI, acts in such a way that, by failing to exercise the duty of care expected of him or her, the AI causes the death or bodily injury to another person, he or she may be held liable for negligent homicide or negligent bodily injury.

Homicide and bodily injury may also be committed by omission, and their negligent form is also punishable. Suppose the perpetrator is under a positive obligation to act and fails to do so because he or she lacks due care and diligence. In that case, he or she may be held liable for homicide or bodily injury by negligence.

- b) Which legal (e.g. criminal, civil) relevance may “defects” or “flaws” in programming, producing or updating an AI system have? Have unforeseen or unforeseeable deviations in the AI decision-making process any legal relevance?

Product liability is relevant from a civil law perspective.

- c) Are there any positive obligations in your domestic legal system (*Garantestellung*), the violation of which could be the ground for criminalising not having avoided an illegal outcome resulting from the functioning of the AI?

Hungarian criminal law doctrine recognises and acknowledges the existence of positive obligations and their effect in establishing criminal liability, but there is no normative basis for this in the Hungarian criminal code. This means that criminal liability based on positive obligations violates the principle of *nullum crimen sine lege*.

The Hungarian criminal law recognises, based on customary law, the duty of the person causing the preventive danger to avert the threat. On this basis, anyone who, whether intentionally or negligently, creates a danger is obliged to deter it or prevent the harmful consequences arising from it. Suppose he fails in this duty, despite having had the opportunity and the ability to do so. He may be held liable as an accessory by omission or as a person guilty of an offence by omission. Aiding and abetting by omission occurs when the offender has a positive obligation to prevent the crime committed by another person but, despite his or her capacity and ability to act, does nothing to stop the offence, provided that he or she knows that it was being committed. This feature of the Hungarian criminal law is also highly questionable from the perspective of the legality principle.

- d) Which standard of care is required from the human agent in developing/programming/producing/selling an AI system?

Do Hungarian literature does not address this issue.

- e) Are there strict liability (secondary or indirect infringement) for harm produced by AI systems?

There are no strict forms of liability in criminal law. There is the legal instrument of product liability and objective liability for hazardous operations in civil law.¹⁰

¹⁰ Hungarian Civil Code Section 6:535 [Liability for hazardous operations] (1) A person who pursues an activity that is considered highly dangerous shall be liable for any damage caused thereby. Where such person is able to prove that the damage occurred due to an unavoidable cause that falls beyond the realm of highly

D) Case law

1) Are there judgments or decisions concerning criminal conduct committed by, or to the detriment of, AI systems?

There is no case law in this regard.

a) If not, please indicate the possible reasons for the lack of judgments (e.g. no complaints by the victims, limited employment of AI systems, etc.).

No cases at all.

2) Are there judgments concerning AI systems relevant for possible criminal consequences?

There is no case law in this regard.

E) Adaptation of Traditional Criminal Law Categories and academic debate

1) Regarding cases involving AI systems in your country, does the case law or the academic debate point out legal issues concerning the traditional categories of the general part of the criminal law?

a) If so, among the following categories, which are those most discussed?

(1) Actus reus

- i. Legal and traditional qualification of the autonomous or independent AI systems agency as “conduct” of the crime
- ii. Legal and traditional qualifications of the autonomous or independent AI systems agency regarding the human conduct
- iii. Influence of the autonomous AI systems agency on the chain of causation

Since most researchers – including criminal law experts – are sceptical about the possible advent of a „strong” AI, discussions on AI as a sui generis actor are limited. According to the current approach, a perpetrator can only be a natural person (over a specific age limit, with a certain level of competency of mind). Therefore, any possible act of an AI is an indirect act of a natural person. However, some researchers argue for a model law that could be prepared in advance and could enter into force immediately when a „strong” AI has been discovered (evolved).

(2) Causality

- i. Interruptions of the chain of causation between the AI systems

dangerous activities, he shall be relieved from liability. (2) These provisions on liability for hazardous operations shall also apply to persons who cause damage to other persons through activities that endanger the human environment. (3) Any exclusion or limitation of liability shall be null and void; this prohibition shall not apply to damage caused to a tangible thing.

- agency and the crime due to errors in programming/producing/maintaining/updating/using
- ii. Use of risk-based legal criteria for the objective charge of the crime to the human agent
 - iii. Interruptions of the chain of causation between the human agent's conduct and the crime due to any anomaly or unpredictability of the output produced by the AI system (e.g. so-called black box problem)

AI can be used as a mere tool to commit crimes. This is when the perpetrator acts on purpose (dolus directus/dolus eventualis). In the cases of negligence (negligent/luxuria), where AI carries out an act – which (if carried out by a natural person) would count as a crime – the liability of at least four categories of natural persons should be taken into consideration: the programmer/manufacturer; the maintenance person; the owner or the user of the AI.

The programmer/manufacturer (Programmer) is responsible for the basic coding of the AI. Suppose the AI is not „general” or human-like in nature (the latter sort of AI is not available yet). In that case, the basic rules of its functioning (e.g. the algorithms by which the AI is capable of machine learning) are written by the Programmer. Of course, the programmer shall not be made responsible for every act of the AI since his/her job is only to make the AI ready for utilisation by a User.

The Owner's responsibility is even more limited if he/she is not the User simultaneously. He/she has no role to play in shaping the AI's cognitive functions or using these functions. More responsibility might occur on the side of the Maintenance person if he/she makes a mistake. His/her liability may be similar to that of the Programmer.

The User has a purpose intended to be reached by using the AI. If the goal is rightful and the User's instructions for the AI were also reasonable and transparent (e.g. without any hints toward any unlawful act to be done by the AI), the User might also not be responsible for the harmful actions of the AI.

As to 1) a) (1) iii. and (2) iii.

At this point, we should consider the final purpose of criminal law itself. Its goal is to release tension, built up in the society, because this tension deteriorates harmonic coexistence in the society, in a regulated form.

It is clear by this definition that any action that may be identified as a criminal act is capable of building up tension that is harmful to society. Therefore, the criminal law answer – sanctions – is a legitimate requirement by the members of society. As we have seen in the previous subpoint (ii), there might be situations where neither the Programmer, the User, nor any other natural person can be made liable for the criminal-like act of the AI that occurs anyway. Now, two options are there to consider:

- 1) not framing anybody as a liable person, because there cannot be found any mistake on anybody's side
- 2) framing the AI.

In option 1) tension will be continuously accumulated in the society, without any release, which might trigger unimaginable events (like anger, political unrest, riots, rebellion, etc.). Option 2) is only available, if

2)a. AI becomes a „Strong”, „General”, or „human-like” – through technological singularity – a fully conscious Artificial Intelligence. It is still the question of the Future.

2)b. at a certain level of autonomy, AI can be declared an „Artificial Person” by the law. It is not without forerunners: legal persons' criminal liability/criminal sanctionability (where the law also creates the „personality” of a non-natural entity) is accepted almost everywhere. The problem with this concept is that – at least in Hungary – in the case of legal persons, there are always natural persons in the background whose liability must be established first. Still, through the academic debate over this paradox of weakness, a model draft law has been made following the example of the liability/sanctionability of legal persons. (See later, in paragraph (5).)

(3) *Principle of culpability* (nullum crimen sine culpa) and *mens rea*

- i. Compliance with the principle of guilt when the output causing the harm generated by the intelligent machine is neither wanted nor predictable by the human agent
- ii. Compliance with the principle of guilt when a human agent intentionally uses an AI system as a tool, but the AI system carried out an offence different from the one wanted by the human agent

Mens Rea is the focal point in much research – outside Hungary. Hungarian researchers are still rather sceptic about the capability of AI (on any level of consciousness and autonomy) as being a specific subject of criminal law. Lately, some publications, conferences and other events (roundtables, etc.) have started to discuss this side of the AI question.

These are the cases where neither a purposeful (dolus directus/dolus eventualis) nor a negligent (negligentia/luxuria) act can be detected on the side of any natural person, and there is no civil liability either, however, the people (the society) require a criminal sanction because the act committed is criminal in nature. So: the AI acts exclusively on its own. As mentioned in the 1) a) (1) iii., in this case, two options are available. Let us now put aside the „not framing anybody” and the „AI as a legal person” options and concentrate solely on the liability of the AI.

Mens Rea is a concept „invented” to distinguish between those humans who can and those who cannot be held criminally responsible. In a broader sense, it can also be a tool to determine those non-humans who can be held accountable from those who cannot. The focal point of the question here is „Mens”, or the conscious mind. Up to the 4th Industrial Revolution/Life 3.0, the conscious mind has been discussed as an exclusive quality of humans. (Ethology research has been conducted to discover and identify some parts of animal behaviour as „conscious”, but pre-eminence and exclusivity of human consciousness have never been questioned.)

If and when technological singularity brings about the age of conscious AIs („Artificial Consciousness”), some traditional categories of criminal law must be reformed. (That is because no criminal act can remain unpunished – and AI will be capable of committing criminal acts on its own purpose, driven by its own will and motivations.) Not all the categories must be reconsidered. Most of them may remain in their original forms, e. g. the concept of culpability: a conscious, „human-like” AI can act on purpose (negligence is much less likely, though¹¹). The academic concept of criminal offence

¹¹ Because of the AI's unequalled cognitive capabilities.

consists of four conjunctive elements in Hungarian criminal law: (1) a criminal offence is human conduct; (2) the conduct fulfils the statutory elements of the definition of a criminal offence (especially in the Special Part of the Criminal Code); (3) the conduct is unlawful; (4) the perpetrator is guilty, and this guilt is in a subjective and not procedural sense.¹² If the condition of guilt (culpability) is reached, most of the categories of the criminal act's definition – moreover, almost the entirety of the the General Part – can be left intact.

The heaviest impact of the „human-like AI” will occur in the General Part's chapters that describe and regulate criminal sanctions and the principles of their application. Existing criminal sanctions have been developed and have a meaning only in the context of human beings. They are unintelligible if they were to be applied for AIs. Let us take the example of deprivation of liberty. It can be described as an act by which a person cannot do whatever he/she wants for some time. The meaning and severity of this sanction are closely connected to time because human life is limited. Therefore, the time has an exceptional value, and the period without liberty on the timeline means the deprivation of a particular value (not exchangeable, not repeatable). Furthermore, human beings have a consciousness of death: biological life always has an end. AIs, on the other hand, have no life limitations; time is not as valuable for them as it is for humans. Criminal sanctions must be reconsidered, and some must be shaped to become applicable to AIs. E. g., erasure of part of the memory can be an adequate sanction – but only if an intact memory has a meaningful value to the AI, deprivation of which causes negative „emotions” like inconvenience (needed for unique prevention) and fear (needed for general prevention¹³). In the case of (3) ii. the conclusion is the same if the AI is conscious and acts independently.

(4) Criminal participation and attempted crimes

- i. Could a human agent be liable for participation in a crime committed or for a harmful result caused by an AI system or AA? Also, for a crime different from the one intended by some of the participants, because of the autonomous and unpredictable functioning of the artificial agent

See above.

- (5) End of the preparatory phase and start of the execution phase: Can acts performed by an AI system or by AA be considered an attempted crime?

See above.

(6) Liability of legal persons

- i. Necessary adjustments of the legal principles on criminal liability of legal persons when they are involved in AI-related crimes
- ii. Necessary adjustments of policies and preventive measures within private organisations to guarantee correct and regular use of AI systems

¹² Krisztina KARSZAI – Zsolt SZOMORA: International Encyclopaedia of Laws, Criminal Law, Hungary, 2015; Alphen aan den Rijn, Hollandia : Kluwer Law International

¹³ lesson to the other AIs through machine learning

2) Which possible solutions have been elaborated to address the questions posed by the unpredictability of the functioning of intelligent systems, especially when the AI system functioning causes an illegal result?

In the case of highly autonomous but not „human-like” AIs, the liability/sanctionability¹⁴ of legal persons may be a good example. There are differences, however.

E.g. in the case of legal persons, there must be (at least in Hungary) a natural person in the „background”. The sanctionability of a legal person must be based on the liability of this natural person. A semi-conscious AI can be evaluated on its own, depending on its level of autonomy.

Nevertheless, a concrete draft model law was created due to an academic project¹⁵.

Main features of the model law:

- **AI sanctionability instead of criminal liability**
- **Specific law instead of part of the Criminal Code**
- **Specific AI definition (main attributes of an AI from the POV of criminal law): „Autonomous Decision-Making Information System” (ADMIS)**
- **the liable perpetrator is a natural person,**
- **if he/she commits the crime with an AI as a tool or**
- **he/she fails to control or use the AI properly**
- **AI can be sanctioned alone if the natural person can not be held liable because of exemptions from criminal responsibility: age, coercion, insanity etc.**
- **Sanctions can be: limiting the functioning of the ADMIS; cancelling the functioning of the ADMIS (as equal to the capital punishment of humans)**

3) Did the legislator or the academic community propose a possible form of criminal liability or a direct sanctioning of AI systems or AA?

Could you please report which form/mode of liability is proposed? (e.g. *direct liability, command responsibility, perpetrator-by-another, probable natural consequence*)

Please describe any proposal made in the literature, highlighting the following aspects:

- a) Elements qualifying the “conduct” of the artificial agent as “conscious and voluntary” (in compliance with the voluntary act requirement)
- b) Forms of blame attributed to AI systems justifying their legal punishment or sanctioning
- c) Possible extension of the traditional categories of intent and negligence or their equivalents
- d) Liability for participation in a crime or attempted crime committed with the use of AI systems or AA
- e) Forms of objective liability/strict liability for AI systems
- f) Types of sanction (criminal punishments or others) to punish AI systems
- g) Measures aiming at avoiding the lack of responsibility of human agents who develop/program/produce/sell AI systems

¹⁴ In Hungary, legal persons cannot be held liable, since liability is attributed only to human beings (natural persons) thus far. Criminal sanctionability is available.

¹⁵ See more [in Hungarian] Barna MISKOLCZI – Zoltán SZATHMÁRY: Criminal Law Challenges in the Age of Informations – Big Data, Profiling and AI. HVG ORAC, Budapest, 2018.

There is no legislative proposal on the table now. As for the academic circle, all the listed considerations are discussed. There is only one model law (see above).

F) Alternatives to criminalisation and non-criminal sources

1) Does domestic law use civil and administrative sanctions (e.g. payment of damages, the closing of enterprise, etc.) to fight abuses of AI systems or harm caused by them?

No, it does not.

2) Is there any form of compulsory civil insurance for damages resulting from an AI system?

No.

3) Are there other technical means for combating AI systems' harm and abuses? (e.g. re-programming the AI system software; destruction of the artificial agent; or similar)?

No.

4) To what extent are users expected to protect themselves (e.g. through security measures in using AI systems; intervention obligations in case of danger, etc.)? What legal relevance could reasonable self-protection of users have in crimes related to AI systems? Could it be a defence for producers accused of an AI-related crime?

Users are expected to protect their personal information while using AI systems. They are usually advised to protect their password, credit card details, etc. before they start using AI. However, high-security measures are not widespread among users. In some cases, the victim's consent can be relevant in criminal cases. It might be an attenuating circumstance in imposing a penalty if the user's omission helped the perpetrator during the crime.

5) To what extent is the product liability legislation applicable to emerging AI employment? Is there a specific regulation for AI systems' testing phase? Alternatively, does the law require simulation obligations?

Product liability legislation is applicable; the development risk clause is adaptable. There are no specific regulations for the testing phase.

6) Are there rules or principles (privacy by design, by default, etc.) on cybersecurity and data protection-relevant to criminal aspects related to the design/production/use/development of AI systems?

The GDPR and Act CXII of 2011 on the Right of Self-Determination concerning Information and the Freedom of Information (Privacy Act) apply. Breaches of GDPR and Privacy Act can constitute a criminal offence if it is perpetrated intentionally under specific circumstances.

7) What is the role of the human agent? What degree of control over the AI system is

granted or required?

A software entity conducts operations in place of users or programs after sensing the environment. According to the current law position, there is no permissibility to allow AI to make completely independent decisions. There is a requirement to ensure that while operating AI, there is a possibility (or, in some cases, obligation) of human intervention in automatic decision-making.

For example, in the case of autonomous vehicles, Decree No. 6/1990 (IV. 12.) in Annex 17 provides that the sensor and control systems of the autonomous vehicle for development purposes must be sufficiently advanced to be able to respond safely to all environmental impacts and road users whom the vehicle may encounter during the test under the supervision or assistance of the test driver.

This obligation is evident in the automated decision-making process from Article 22 of the GDPR.

8) Is there a standardisation of technical rules for designers/programmers/developers/producers of AI systems (or is it in the process of being defined)?

Not yet.

G) Final evaluations and future developments

Please, use the box below for further suggestions and observations concerning current trends on criminal policy strategy regarding AI-related crimes, lack of legislation, legal reforms, law proposals, reports and statistics on the incidence of AI-related crimes, case law, legal debate in your country, etc.

It can be said that there is a growing body of legal literature in this area and that criminal law researchers are also working on these issues. In legal practice, "everyday" data misuse emerges in criminal cases, but as AI (algorithmic decision making) solutions become more widespread, these issues will also appear in courtrooms.